

Appendix (ii): IDI Topic guides for breastfeeding women (V1.0 14-08-2023)

Participant ID # _____ Interviewer Name: _____ Date _____ Audio file#:

Participant type [tick as appropriate]: On medication.....Not medication.....

Warm up [socio-demographic information]

- i) Town/Village of residence _____ ii) Marital status _____
_____ iii) Education level _____
_____ iv) Marital status: Married/living with partner
Separated/divorce Single Widowed
v) What do you do for a living? _____
vi) How old are you? 18-24 _____ 25-34 _____ 35-44
>45yrs.....

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vii) How did you deliver your

current breastfeeding baby?

- a) Spontaneous vaginal delivery....
b) Caesarean section.....

viii) How many children have you breastfed? _____

ix) If yes, which medication are you taking? Tick where appropriate.

- _____ a) Anti-tuberculosis drugs _____
b) Anti-Malarial drug
c) Anti-retroviral drugs
d) Anti-hypertensive drugs
e) Diabetic drugs
f) Other; specify.....
.....

A. Breastfeeding

L Please tell me about your experiences of breastfeeding?

o PROBE any challenges faced during breastfeeding?

2. What do you normally do for your health when you are breastfeeding?

- o PROBE about participant's health seeking behaviour during breast feeding o
PROBE about cultural norms, beliefs and practices relating to breastfeeding and care in
the community o PROBE about the use of traditional birth attendants/herbalist
(experience of use and reasons for use)

3. Tell me what you know about the importance of breastfeeding? o

PROBE: what is the purpose of breastfeeding?

- o PROBE: It is recommended that women start breastfeeding in the first 1 to 2 hours
after delivery. Is that feasible?

- o PROBE: why do you think it is ideal for women to exclusively breastfeed?
Why?
 - o PROBE: when do you think is ideal for women to start introducing foods to the baby, while breastfeeding? Why? B. Breast feeding and medication.
4. What do you think about the use of medication during breast feeding?
5. Please tell me about your experiences of breastfeeding while on medication
- PROBE: Did you face any challenges?
 - PROBE: How well are _____ you _____ taking _____ your medications now that you are breastfeeding?
 - PROBE: Do you face any challenges with adherence? ● PROBE: How about the kind of medications used; if and what side effects suffered; and how these may have affected adherence.
 - PROBE: about the specific challenges that breastfeeding poses to adherence.
6. What would you suggest to a friend who needs to take medications during breastfeeding?
7. How do you find out the safety of medication taken during breastfeeding? ● PROBE: if they check leaflet for dispensed drug

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- PROBE: Do you ask a health worker
- PROBE: Do you search from the internet websites.
- 8. What could be the risks involved in self-medication during breast feeding? ● PROBE: Drugs may cause side effects to the breast fed Infant
 - PROBE: Drugs may reduce milk production
 - PROBE: Drugs may cause death to the Infant
- 9. What do you think can be done differently to improve medication use among breastfeeding women?
 - PROBE: what support do breastfeed women need with their treatment/medications? _____ ●
 - PROBE: what changes would you like to be made within and outside the facility to help breastfeeding women adhere to medications?
 - PROBE: what kind of incentives will motivate breastfeeding women to adhere?
- 10. Where do you get information about medication use during pregnancy and breastfeeding?
 - PROBE: consultation from a health worker
 - PROBE: Consultation from a relative/friend ● PROBE: Internet website

C. Breast feeding and medications disclosure.

- 11. What do you think about disclosure of any medications to your partner?
 - PROBE: What motivates you to tell him?
 - PROBE: How easy or difficult was it for you to tell him? Did you have any worries/anxiety about telling him? If yes, how? ● PROBE: Describe how you went about telling him.
 - PROBE: Who else among your significant others (e.g. friends, family members) did you tell? Why them?
 - PROBE: Why do you think other women in this community find it difficult to disclose their medications to their partners?
- 12. What has been your living experience while on medication in a non-disclosure status, If never disclosure?
- 13. In what ways do you think disclosure or the lack of it affect medications uptake and adherence among breastfeeding women in this community?
 - Probe how disclosure or the lack of it may have had negative or positive effects on treatment uptake and/or adherence.
- 14. How can breast feeding women be supported to disclose safely their medications?
 - PROBE: what support do you need to disclose safely to your partner? [IF UNDISCLOSED] _○ PROBE: what support do women need to disclose safely?
 - PROBE: how would you recommend breastfeeding women go about disclosing their medications to their partners in a safe manner?
 - PROBE: when is it safe to disclose and when is it not safe to disclose to one's partner, and why?

D. Study participation and Partner consent in study participation?

- 15. What was or what has been your experience in study participation, if any? ○ PROBE: Did you face any challenges? How?
- 16. Why do you think about breastfeeding women's participation in studies?

17. Why do you think about breastfeeding women's exclusion in studies?

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18. What is your thought about breastfeeding women seeking consent from partners for study participation?

● PROBE: For reasons given for the respective responses.

E. Breast feeding and Herbs, complementary and alternative medications.

19. What do you think about the use of herbs and complementary medicines during breastfeeding?

● PROBE: if used herbal medicines

● PROBE: if used dietary supplements

● PROBE: if used homeopathic preparations

● PROBE: if used traditional and natural preparations practices (Garlic, eggplants, yeast, alcohol)

● PROBE: if used any other, and reasons for use.

● PROBE: Any side effects encountered?

● PROBE: Benefits

20. Should the need arise, which one would you prefer, drug or herbal/CAM medicines?

21. What do you think about the use of herbs, complementary and alternative medicines during breast feeding?

PROBE: Any side effects encountered?

PROBE: Benefits

22. What would you suggest to a friend who needs to take herbs, and CAM during breastfeeding?

Conclusion

Is there anything else you would like to add to what we have discussed?

Appendix (iv): IDIs Topic guide for Partners of breast-feeding women (v 1.0, 14-08-2023)

Date | IDI #

A. Medications and breastfeeding.

1. What are women's practices during breastfeeding?

o PROBE: Cultural norms, beliefs and practices relating to pregnancy/breastfeeding and care

2. What do you think about partner support for women during breastfeeding? o PROBE: How men in the community support their partners o PROBE: what reasons some men have for supporting their partners o PROBE: what reasons some men have for not supporting their partners o PROBE: challenges men face with supporting their partners while breastfeeding and taking medications

3. What do you think about disclosure of medicines that you are taking to your partner? o PROBE: what reasons do women in this community have for not disclosing? o PROBE: what strategies do

women employ to keep their disease status secret? o PROBE: In what ways does disclosure or the lack of it affect women's medication uptake and adherence?

4. What kind of support do breast feeding women need to enable them take drugs well?
 - o PROBE: How should women proceed with disclosing their disease status to their partners?
 - o PROBE: How do men expect their partners to disclose their disease status?
 - o PROBE: when is it safe to disclose and when is it not safe to disclose, and why?
 5. How have you supported your partner while breastfeeding and taking medication?
- B. Study Participation

6. Please tell me what you think about breastfeeding women's participation in studies?
 - PROBE: Reasons for women participation or not?
 - PROBE: Knowledge about female partners participating in research.
 - PROBE: Would you or men in the community allow your pregnant or breast-feeding wife to participate in research? Explain
7. How do men influence their partners in decision making to participate in clinical trials/studies while breastfeeding?
 - o PROBE: who are the decision makers? o PROBE: what role do men play? o PROBE: what role do women play?
 - o PROBE: about how decisions and disagreements about participation are negotiate and resolve within the family
8. What are your thoughts about partner consent in study participation?
 - o PROBE: Would you recommend men to allow their partners participate in research while pregnant or breast feeding?
 - o PROBE: Why do you think it is important to include pregnant and breastfeeding women in researches?
9. What advice would you give to encourage breast-feeding women participate in researches?

Conclusion

Is there anything else you would like to add to what we have discussed?